

United States Department of the Interior

FISH AND WILDLIFE SERVICE
San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office
650 Capitol Mall, Suite 8-300
Sacramento, California 95814

In reply refer to:
2022-0035037

September 16, 2022

Ms. Lindsay Vivian
California Department of Transportation
District 4
Office of Biological Sciences and Permits
111 Grand Ave, MS-8E
Oakland, CA 94612

Subject: Formal Consultation on the State Route 61 Capital Preventative Maintenance Project in Alameda County, California

Dear Ms. Vivian:

This letter is in response to the California Department of Transportation (Caltrans) April 22, 2022, request for initiation of formal consultation with the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (Service) on the proposed State Route 61 (SR 61) Capital Preventative Maintenance Project (Project) in Alameda County, California. At issue are the proposed project's effects on the federally endangered salt marsh harvest mouse (*Reithrodontomys raviventris*) and California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*). Regarding taxonomic assignment and nomenclature for the California clapper rail, until a time when the Service officially adopts changes made by the American Ornithologists' Union (from California clapper rail [*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*] to Ridgway's rail [*Rallus obsoletus*]), the Service maintains the use of California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*) as used in this current correspondence. This response is provided under the authority of the Endangered Species Act of 1973, as amended (16 U.S.C. 1531 *et seq.*) (Act), and in accordance with the implementing regulations pertaining to interagency cooperation (50 CFR 402).

The Federal action on which we are consulting is Caltrans' proposed plan to conduct preventative maintenance along a section of SR 61. Pursuant to 50 CFR 402.12(j), you submitted a biological assessment for our review and requested concurrence with the findings presented therein. These findings conclude that the proposed project may affect, and is likely to adversely affect the federally endangered salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail.

In considering your request, we based our evaluation on the following: (1) Caltrans' April 22, 2022, letter requesting initiation of formal consultation and the enclosed Biological Assessment; (2) email correspondence between the Service and Caltrans; and (3) other information available to the Service.

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The remainder of this document provides our biological opinion on the effects of the proposed Project on the federally endangered salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail.

Consultation History

- March 18, 2022: Caltrans requested technical assistance from the Service for this Project.
- March 23, 2022: The Service and Caltrans had an online meeting to discuss this Project.
- April 22, 2022: The Service received a request for formal consultation and a biological assessment from Caltrans.

BIOLOGICAL OPINION

Description of the Proposed Action

The purpose of the Project is to preserve and extend the life of the existing pavement, improve its ride quality, and enhance the traffic safety within this corridor on SR 61 from post mile (PM) 14.8 to PM 19.8 and reduce the potential and severity of run-off-road type accidents in the cities of San Leandro, Oakland, and Alameda in Alameda County. The 2016 Automated Pavement Condition Survey Report from the Pavem pavement management tool shows an overall fair condition for the portion of SR 61 that the Project covers. However, Caltrans identified locations that exhibit high alligator B cracking, which leads to unacceptable ride quality. If left untreated, major roadway rehabilitation will be required in the near future.

An additional need for this Project is to reduce the potential and severity of run-off-road type accidents into the San Leandro Bay and to bring existing guardrails up to current Caltrans standards. Accident data from the Traffic Accident Surveillance and Analysis System indicates that SR 61 has higher fatality rates than statewide average accident rates due to these types of accidents.

Pavement Maintenance

Caltrans proposes to cold plane three inches of the entire asphalt concrete (AC) pavement along the length of the Project (PM 14.8 to PM 19.8). SR 61, within the Project limits, is mainly one or two lanes in each northbound and southbound direction. AC digouts will also be performed at heavily distressed pavement within the Project limits. AC pavement will be replaced with Hot Mix Asphalt Type A leveling course followed by 1.8 inches of Rubberized Hot Mix Asphalt.

Additionally, the pavement structural section, driveways, and curb ramps at Eden Road (PM 15.16) will be reconstructed due to heavy pavement damage. The unpaved area between the northbound edge of shoulder and the bike lane (approximately PM 17.90) will be regraded to provide positive drainage or provide a new inlet and pipe connection to the nearby inlet at approximately PM 17.93. Rumble strips will also be established along the outside shoulders of the travel lanes from PM 16.47 to PM 17.50.

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Replacement of Metal Beam Guardrail

Several locations within the Project limits have existing metal beam guardrail that does not meet current Caltrans standards. At these locations, outdated Metal Beam Guardrail (MBGR) will be replaced with Midwest Guardrail Systems (MGS). The Project will install MGS along northbound SR 61 from PM 17.44 to PM 17.52 and from PM 17.87 to PM 18.00. MGS will also be installed along southbound SR 61 between Swan Way and Langley Street (PM 16.47 to PM 17.02). The maximum depth of excavation for the guardrail posts is expected to be 6 feet maximum. At locations with narrow embankments, the depth of excavation for the post will be approximately 4.5 feet. At locations with very narrow embankments and/or tide erosion issues, a Guardrail Concrete Beam system to a depth of 2.5 feet will be explored.

Curb Ramp Improvements

A total of 52 existing curbs within the Project limits do not meet current Caltrans standards and will be upgraded with Americans with Disabilities Act (ADA) -compliant curb ramps. This will include removal and replacement of sidewalk structural layer to a depth of one foot. The existing drainage inlets (DI) may need to be replaced in-kind or moved during curb ramp improvements. Drainage modification is not anticipated to cause significant changes in local hydrology or water quality that would require permit approval. However, the curb ramp upgrade work in the City of Alameda is expected to involve significant drainage modification work.

Right of Way Requirement

All project activities are anticipated to be within the Caltrans right of way (ROW). There are no right of way acquisitions or temporary construction easements anticipated.

Drainage Work

Significant drainage modification is expected during the curb ramp upgrade work in the City of Alameda due to drainage conduits being shallow and existing under the sidewalk at many curb returns.

To alleviate surface water ponding, an additional drainage inlet and pipe connection will need to be installed at approximately PM 17.90, which is adjacent to San Leandro Bay on northbound SR 61. The new drainage inlet will be placed in the road shoulder and connected to the existing stormwater drain system draining into San Leandro Bay. All work will occur in barren and paved areas within the Project Construction Area (PCA). A maximum of a 3.5-foot depth of excavation is anticipated for the inlet and pipe construction.

Staging/Equipment Laydown Areas/Access Routes

Staging and equipment laydown areas may be established anywhere within the Caltrans ROW of the PCA in paved and unpaved areas. There is one planned staging laydown area (5,800 square feet) south of PM 17.44 on the southbound side of SR 61. A second planned staging area (2,000 square feet) is located on the northbound side of SR 61, just east of Island Drive, where some

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ruderal vegetation removal is expected (See Table 1). No staging or equipment storage will occur in areas considered to be suitable habitat for listed species, or wetlands and other waters. Wetlands and other waters adjacent to staging areas will be delineated for construction personnel with Environmentally Sensitive Area (ESA) fencing, or other appropriate delineator.

Traffic Impacts

To complete construction, shoulder and lane closures are expected. Half road closures may also be necessary.

Work will likely be confined behind temporary railing to provide greater separation of construction personnel from roadway traffic.

Construction Schedule

The work will mainly be done during the day on weekdays. However, some night work is expected, and the contractor will be allowed to work weekends if necessary. Construction will be completed within approximately 2 years. Construction activities between PM 17.5 and PM 18 are anticipated to take 90 days to complete.

Miscellaneous Project Activities

Additional activities associated with the Project include the installation of concrete vegetation control along northbound SR 61 from PM 17.44 to PM 17.52 and from PM 17.86 to PM 18.00. A portion of the vegetation control may need to be converted to a flat v-ditch. All existing Transportation Management Systems (TMS) elements that have been previously damaged will be replaced. All traffic striping, pavement markings, and pavement markers will be reinstated to meet current standards. Crosswalk markings will be enhanced by providing a 12-inch (white) limit line, 5 feet in advance of the crosswalk line on both directions of SR 61. The Project will also install new signage at approximately PM 19.3 on southbound SR 61 and will replace signage at approximately PM 19 on northbound SR 61.

Table 1. Land Cover Areas in the Action Area

Land Cover Type	Total Area (Acres)	Temporary Impacts (Acres)	Permanent Impacts (Acres)	Total Impacts (Acres)
Road	45.708	0.000	0.000	0.000
Barren Soil	0.255	0.000	0.000	0.000
Coastal Salt Marsh	2.567	0.000	0.000	0.000
Other waters of the U.S.	1.347	0.000	0.000	0.000
Urban Landscaped/Ruderal	16.085	0.179	0.073	0.388
Total Area (Acres)	65.962	0.179	0.073	0.388

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Conservation Measures

1. *Biological Opinion.* Caltrans will include a copy of the biological opinion within its solicitations for design and construction of the Project making the primary contractor responsible for implementing all requirements and obligations included within the biological opinion, and to educate and inform all other contractors involved in the project as to the requirements of the biological opinion. The resident engineer or their designee would be responsible for implementing the *Conservation Measures* and *Terms and Conditions* of the biological opinion. The resident engineer or their designee would maintain a copy of the biological opinion on site whenever construction is taking place. Their name and telephone number would be provided to the Service at least 30 calendar days prior to groundbreaking at the project. Prior to groundbreaking, the resident engineer would submit a letter to the Service verifying that they possess a copy of the biological opinion and have read the *Terms and Conditions*.
2. *Service-Approved Biological Monitors.* Caltrans would submit the names and qualifications of the proposed biological monitor(s) for the Service approval prior to initiating construction activities for the Project. Only Service-approved biological monitors would implement the monitoring duties outlined in the biological opinion including delivery of the Worker Environmental Awareness Training Program. The Service-Approved Biological Monitor(s) will keep a copy of the biological opinion in their possession when on-site. Through communication with the resident engineer, the Service-Approved Biological Monitor(s) will be on-site during all work that could reasonably result in the take of the salt marsh harvest mouse. The Service-Approved Biological Monitor(s) will have the authority to stop work that may result in the unauthorized take of special status species. If the Service-Approved Biological Monitor exercises this authority, the Service will be notified by telephone and e-mail message within one (1) working day.
3. *Listed Species in Construction Zones.* The resident engineer would immediately contact the Service-Approved Biological Monitor(s) and the Service in the event that a salt marsh harvest mouse or California clapper rail gains access to a construction zone. The resident engineer would suspend construction activities within a 250-foot radius of the animal that could reasonably result in a take of the listed species until the animal leaves the site voluntarily.
4. *Worker Environmental Awareness Training.* All construction personnel would attend a mandatory environmental education program delivered by a Service-Approved Biological Monitor prior to working in the PCA. The program would focus on the conservation measures that are relevant to employee's personal responsibility and would include an explanation as how to best avoid take of sensitive species. Distributed materials would include a pamphlet with distinguishing photographs of sensitive species, species' habitat requirements, compliance reminders, and relevant contact information. Documentation of the training, including sign-in sheets, would be kept on file and would be available on request.
5. *Preconstruction Surveys Prior to Initial Ground Disturbance.* In areas with potential habitat for listed species and immediately prior to any ground disturbance, including staging of

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equipment or materials, preconstruction surveys would be conducted by a Service-Approved Biological Monitor. These surveys would consist of walking surveys of the project limits and accessible adjacent areas within at least 50 feet of the project limits to determine presence of the species. If a listed species is observed, all project work within the vicinity would cease and the Service would be contacted to determine how to proceed. Under no circumstances would the capture, handling or relocation of salt marsh harvest mice or California clapper rails occur unless expressly authorized by the Service.

6. *Construction Monitoring.* A Service-Approved Biological Monitor would be present to monitor for salt marsh harvest mice and California clapper rails prior to and during construction activities adjacent to suitable habitat. The biological monitor would have the authority to stop work if deemed necessary for any reason to protect the species. If a listed species is observed in the work area, work would be stopped immediately by the biological monitor until the individual(s) leaves the work area on its own volition. If the individual(s) does not leave the work area, work would not be reinitiated until after the Service has been contacted and a decision reached on how construction activities could proceed. The project resident engineer or construction inspector would consult with the biological monitor on how to proceed.
7. *Environmentally Sensitive Area Fencing.* Prior to commencing construction work along Doolittle Drive southbound (PM 17.44 to PM 18.02), areas of suitable habitat for listed species that are adjacent to the construction zone will be delineated with high visibility temporary fencing at least 4 feet in height, or other appropriate delineator, to prevent encroachment of construction personnel and equipment onto sensitive areas during construction. The fencing will be removed when all construction equipment is removed from the site. Installation of fencing outside of the edges of the PCA is not warranted due to the short duration of construction and potential for fencing to cause unnecessary impacts to sensitive habitats during fence installation.
8. *Major Tides and Construction.* During periods of forecast extreme high tides (e.g., spring or king), all construction activities would temporarily cease within 100 feet of suitable refugia habitat for salt marsh harvest mice and California clapper rail. Extreme tides may also occur during weather events (e.g., storms or high winds) that coincide with average high tide events, and those combined phenomena can push water into normally dry zones. Work also should not occur during the three hours before and after the predicted high tide event. Refugia habitat is defined as high marsh or adjacent transitional areas, including ruderal sites, which are not expected to be inundated during the extreme tidal event. A temporary halt to construction activities would allow individual animals the opportunity to move into refugia habitat without disturbance from construction activities.
9. *Seasonal Avoidance for California Clapper Rail Nesting.* Construction will be restricted to the period between September 1 and January 31 for work adjacent to suitable nesting habitat for California clapper rail along a stretch of Doolittle Drive within the Project (PM 17.44 to PM 18.02).

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10. *Covering of Trenches & Excavated Holes.* To prevent inadvertent entrapment of listed species (i.e., salt marsh harvest mouse) during construction, excavated holes or electrical trenches more than 1 foot deep with walls steeper than 30 degrees would be covered by plywood or similar materials at the close of each working day. Alternatively, an additional 4-foot-high vertical barrier, independent of exclusionary fences, would be used to further prevent the inadvertent entrapment of listed species. If it is not feasible to cover an excavation or provide an additional 4-foot-high vertical barrier, independent of exclusionary fences, one or more escape ramps constructed of earth fill or wooden planks would be installed. Before such holes or trenches are filled, they would be thoroughly inspected for trapped animals. If at any time a trapped listed animal is discovered, the Service-Approved Biological Monitor would immediately place escape ramps or other appropriate structures to allow the animal to escape or the Service would be contacted by telephone for guidance. The Service would be notified of the incident by telephone and electronic mail.
11. *Vegetation Removal.* Vegetation removal would be minimized to the maximum extent practicable. Prior to removal of vegetation a Service-Approved Biological Monitor will inspect suitable habitat for signs of harvest mice species or other sensitive species. Following inspection, personnel, under the supervision of the Service-Approved Biological Monitor, will disturb vegetation to encourage movement of individuals into adjacent marsh areas (i.e., flush). Vegetation will be removed using hand tools (e.g., string trimmers) and trimmed down to no taller than 2 inches. Trimming will begin farthest away from marsh or pickleweed habitat and proceed toward the remaining habitat.
12. Vegetation within the PCA footprint that is closer than 50 feet of the edge of pickleweed vegetation will be removed.
13. *Nighttime Construction.* To the extent practicable, nighttime construction would be minimized.
14. *Artificial Lighting.* Except when necessary for construction, driver, or pedestrian safety, lighting of the proposed PCA by artificial lighting during nighttime hours would be minimized to the maximum extent practicable. If nighttime work is required, construction personnel will turn portable tower lights on no more than 30 minutes before the beginning of civil twilight, and off no more than 30 minutes after the end of civil sunrise. Portable tower lights will have directional shields attached to them, and personnel will only direct lights downward and toward active construction and staging areas. Lighting per portable tower light will not exceed 2,000 lumens. To the extent practicable, personnel will only use enough coverage to light the travel way, median, and staging areas. If onsite staging areas require security lighting, that lighting installation will be in accordance with this measure to the extent practicable.
15. *Vehicle Use.* Vehicle use near suitable habitat for the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail would be minimized to the maximum extent practicable. Vehicles would remain on paved roads to the maximum extent practicable, and speeds would be limited to 10 miles per hour when off the pavement.

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16. *Dust Control.* Dust control measures would consist of regular truck watering of construction access areas and disturbed soil areas with the use of organic soil stabilizers to minimize airborne dust and soil particles generated from graded areas. Regular truck watering would be a requirement of the construction contract. In addition, for disturbed soil areas, an organic tackifier to control dust emissions blowing off of the right-of-way or out of the construction area during construction would be included in the contract special provisions. Watering guidelines for dewatering would be established to avoid any excessive run-off that may flow into contiguous areas. Any material stockpiles would be watered, sprayed with tackifier, or covered, to minimize dust production and wind erosion.
17. *Trash.* All food-related trash items such as wrappers, cans, bottles, and food scraps would be disposed of in closed containers and removed regularly from the work area.
18. *Firearms.* No firearms would be allowed in the Action Area except for those carried by authorized security personnel, or local, State, or Federal law enforcement officials.
19. *Pets.* To prevent harassment, injury, or mortality of sensitive species, no pets would be permitted in the action area.
20. *Caltrans Standard Best Management Practices (BMPs).* The potential for adverse effects to water quality will be avoided by implementing temporary and permanent BMPs outlined in Section 7-1.01G of the Caltrans Standard Specifications. Caltrans erosion control BMPs will be used to minimize any wind or water-related erosion. The State Water Resources Control Board (SWRCB) has issued a National Pollution Discharge Elimination System (NPDES) Statewide Storm Water Permit to Caltrans to regulate storm water and non-storm water discharges from Caltrans facilities. A Storm Water Pollution Prevention Program (SWPPP) or Water Pollution Control Program (WPCP) will be developed for the Project, as required. The SWPPP or WPCP complies with the Caltrans Storm Water Management Plan (SWMP). The SWMP includes guidance for Project design staff to include provisions in construction contracts to include measures to protect sensitive areas and to prevent and minimize storm water and non-storm water discharges. The SWPPP or WPCP will reference the Caltrans Construction Site BMPs Manual. This manual is comprehensive and includes many other protective measures and guidance to prevent and minimize pollutant discharges and can be found at the following website: <http://www.dot.ca.gov/hq/construc/stormwater/manuals.htm>

Protective measures will be included in the contract, including, at a minimum:

- a. No discharge of pollutants from vehicle and equipment cleaning are allowed into storm drains or water courses.
- b. Vehicle and equipment fueling and maintenance operations must be at least 50 feet away from water courses.
- c. Concrete wastes are collected in washouts and water from curing operations is collected and disposed of and not allowed into water courses.

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- d. Dust control would be implemented, including use of water trucks and tackifiers to control dust in excavation and fill areas, rocking temporary access road entrances and exits, and covering temporary stockpiles when weather conditions require.
 - e. Coir rolls would be installed along or at the base of slopes during construction to capture sediment and temporary organic hydro-mulching would be applied to all unfinished disturbed and graded areas.
 - f. Work areas where temporary disturbance has removed the pre-existing vegetation would be restored and re-seeded with a native seed mix.
 - g. Graded areas would be protected from erosion using a combination of silt fences, fiber rolls along toe of slopes or along edges of designated staging areas, and erosion-control netting (such as jute or coir) as appropriate.
 - h. A Revegetation Plan would be prepared for restoration of temporary staging areas.
21. *Mono-filament Netting*. To prevent listed species from being entangled, trapped, or injured, erosion control materials with plastic mono-filament netting would not be used within the Action Area.
 22. *Asphalt Waste*. All grindings and asphaltic-concrete waste will be stored within previously disturbed areas absent of habitat and at a minimum of 150 feet from any aquatic habitat, culvert, or drainage feature.
 23. *Replanting with Native Species*. All staging areas that are temporarily affected during construction will be revegetated with native plant species appropriate to the habitat that was disturbed in order to restore habitat values. Invasive, exotic plants will be controlled within the PCA to the maximum extent practicable, pursuant to Executive Order 13112 (Invasive Species).
 24. *Care of Injured or Dead Species*. Listed species found injured will be cared for by a Service-Approved Biological Monitor (s), licensed veterinarian, or a wildlife rehabilitation facility. Dead individuals of any listed species will be preserved by freezing and held in a secure location. The Service will be notified of the discovery within one (1) working day of death or injury to a listed species occurring as a result of project-related activities or if observed at the project site. Notification will include the date, time, and location clearly indicated on a United States Geological Survey (USGS) 7½-minute quadrangle or other maps at a finer scale, as requested by the Service, and any other pertinent information. Dead individual animals will be placed in a zippered plastic storage bag with a piece of paper stating where and when the animal was found and the name of the person who found it. The bag will be frozen in a freezer in a secure location until instructions are received from the agency regarding the disposition of the specimen or until the agency takes custody of the specimen.
 25. *Post-construction Compliance Report*: Caltrans will submit post-construction compliance reports prepared by the Service-Approved Biological Monitor to the Service within 60

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calendar days following completion of project activities or within 60 calendar days of any break in construction activity lasting more than 60 calendar days. This report will detail: (1) dates that relevant project activities occurred; (2) pertinent information concerning the success of the project in implementing the Conservation Measures for listed species; (3) an explanation of failure to meet such measures, if any; (4) known project effects on listed species, if any; (5) occurrences of incidental take of any listed species, if any; (6) documentation of employee environmental education; and (7) other pertinent information. The reports will be addressed to the Section 7 Division Manager, San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office.

26. *Service Access*: If requested, Caltrans will allow access by Service personnel into the Project footprint to inspect the Project and its activities.

27. *Reinitiating Consultation*. Caltrans will reinitiate consultation if the Project results in effects to listed species not considered in the biological opinion.

Action Area

The Action Area is defined in 50 CFR § 402.02, as “all areas to be affected directly or indirectly by the Federal action and not merely the immediate area involved in the action.” For the proposed Project, the Action Area is approximately 65.96 acres and includes the entire PCA and adjacent areas. The Project is located in San Leandro and Oakland East USGS 7.5-minute topographic quadrangles. This includes construction-related noise, vibration, ground disturbance, vegetation removal, and compaction.

Analytical Framework for the Jeopardy Determination

Section 7(a)(2) of the Act requires that Federal agencies ensure that any action they authorize, fund, or carry out is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species. “Jeopardize the continued existence of” means to engage in an action that reasonably would be expected, directly or indirectly, to reduce appreciably the likelihood of both the survival and recovery of a listed species in the wild by reducing the reproduction, numbers, or distribution of that species (50 CFR § 402.02).

The jeopardy analysis in this biological opinion considers the effects of the proposed Federal action, and any cumulative effects, on the rangewide survival and recovery of the listed species. It relies on four components: (1) the *Status of the Species*, which describes the current rangewide condition of the species, the factors responsible for that condition, and its survival and recovery needs; (2) the *Environmental Baseline*, which analyzes the current condition of the species in the Action Area without the consequences to the listed species caused by the proposed action, the factors responsible for that condition, and the relationship of the Action Area to the survival and recovery of the species; (3) the *Effects of the Action*, which includes all effects that are caused by the proposed Federal action; and (4) the *Cumulative Effects*, which evaluates the effects of future, non-Federal activities in the Action Area on the species. The *Effects of the Action* and *Cumulative Effects* are added to the *Environmental Baseline* and in light of the status

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of the species, the Service formulates its opinion as to whether the proposed action is likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species.

Status of the Species

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

There are two subspecies of the salt marsh harvest mouse: the northern subspecies (*R. r. halicoetes*) and the southern subspecies (*R. r. raviventris*) both of which are listed as endangered. Information about the salt marsh harvest mouse biology and ecology is available in the *Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California*, available at: https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/recovery_plan/TMRP/20130923_TMRP_Books_Signed_FINAL.pdf (Service 2013). Critical habitat has not been designated for this species. Threats evaluated during the drafting of the recovery plan and discussed in the final document have continued to act on the species since its publication, with loss of habitat being the most significant effect. For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species' range-wide status, please refer to the salt marsh harvest mouse 5-year review at https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/tess/species_nonpublish/3643.pdf (Service 2021). No change in the species' listing status was recommended in this 5-year review.

California Clapper Rail

Information about the California clapper rail biology and ecology is available in the *Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California*, available at: https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/recovery_plan/TMRP/20130923_TMRP_Books_Signed_FINAL.pdf (Service 2013). Critical habitat has not been designated for this species. For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species' range-wide status, please refer to the California clapper rail 5-year Review, available at https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/five_year_review/doc6592.pdf (Service 2020). No change in the species' listing status was recommended in this 5-year review. Threats evaluated during that review and discussed in the final document have continued to act on the species with loss of habitat being the most significant effect.

Environmental Baseline

Environmental Baseline refers to the condition of the listed species or its designated critical habitat in the Action Area, without the consequences to the listed species or designated critical habitat caused by the proposed action. The environmental baseline includes the past and present impacts of all Federal, State, or private actions and other human activities in the Action Area, the anticipated impacts of all proposed Federal projects in the Action Area that have already undergone formal or early section 7 consultation, and the impact of State or private actions which are contemporaneous with the consultation in process. The consequences to listed species or designated critical habitat from ongoing agency activities or existing agency facilities that are not within the agency's discretion to modify are part of the *Environmental Baseline*. The following habitat types occur within the Action Area.

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Coastal Salt Marsh

Coastal salt marshes are subject to tidal inundation by salt water for at least part of the year and are dominated by low-growing, herbaceous, salt-tolerant hydrophytic plants at moderate to dense cover. The dominant herbaceous species within the salt marsh are pickleweed (*Sarcocornia pacifica*), cattail (*Typha spp.*), and salt marsh bulrush (*Bolboschoenus maritimus*). Listed wildlife species with potential to utilize coastal salt marsh include the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail. Coastal salt marsh totals 2.567 acres in Fan Marsh within the Action Area, adjacent to PM 17.44 to PM 18.02.

Urban Landscaped/Ruderal

Urban landscaped and ruderal areas are the primary vegetated land cover types within the Action Area. Ruderal areas have been impacted by grading, mowing, and filling. Ruderal roadside vegetation is composed primarily of weedy, non-native plants, such as black mustard (*Brassica nigra*), poison hemlock (*Conium maculatum*), wild fennel (*Foeniculum vulgare*), Italian thistle (*Carduus pycnocephalus*), and bristly ox-tongue (*Helminthotheca echioides*). Ruderal vegetation is not a natural vegetation type, and there is no equivalent alliance in A Manual of California Vegetation (Sawyer *et al.* 2009). Urban landscaped and ruderal vegetation occur in close proximity to SR 61 within the Action Area and total approximately 16.085 acres.

Ruderal habitats are capable of supporting a number of bird species associated with urban environments, and which are known to be tolerant of disturbance by human activities, such as wrentits (*Chamaea fasciata*), bushtits (*Psaltiriparus minimus*), oak titmouse (*Baeolophus inornatus*), chestnut-backed chickadee (*Poecile rufescens*), and California quail (*Callipepla californica*). Gopher snake (*Pituophis catenifer catenifer*) and western fence lizard (*Sceloporus occidentalis*) also occur in this zone (Mayer and Laudenslayer 1988). Due to the disturbed nature of this habitat, it is not generally considered to have conditions suitable for listed species.

Waters

Waters within the Action Area include open water and culverted water adjacent to both northbound and southbound lanes of SR 61 along Doolittle Drive. Ruderal and wetland vegetation border the roadway along Doolittle Drive. Waters total approximately 1.347 acre in the Action Area.

Road/Barren Soil

The Action Area is mostly comprised of paved roadways and portions of barren soil along the road shoulder. Road/barren soil surfaces comprise approximately 45.963 acres within the Action Area. Road/Barren Soil land cover is frequently disturbed and does not provide habitat for most species. This busy road creates noise, vibration, and visual disturbance from substantial vehicle use.

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Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

No salt marsh harvest mouse surveys were conducted for the proposed action. Caltrans relied on habitat assessments and best-available scientific and commercial data, including a literature search to evaluate the potential for the occurrence of this species or its habitat in the Action Area. A habitat assessment on February 18, 2022 confirmed that salt marsh harvest mouse should be considered to have potential to occur in the Action Area.

Stands of pickleweed marsh habitat are located adjacent to the Action Area on Doolittle Drive between Island Drive and Langley Street. The cover of pickleweed here is moderate. Interspersed with the pickleweed are patches of bare ground and other wetland-tolerant plants.

There is one documented occurrence of salt marsh harvest mouse within two miles of the Action Area, in Arrowhead Marsh, which is northeast of the Action Area, across Airport Channel (California Natural Diversity Database (CNDDDB) occurrence # 59) (California Department of Fish and Wildlife (CDFW) 2022). Salt marsh harvest mice have been known to occur in nearby Arrowhead Marsh and may appear in portions of the Action Area that contain similar habitat. As a result, there is potential for salt marsh harvest mouse to be present near or in the Action Area that is adjacent to Fan Marsh (PM 17.44 to PM 18.02). The ruderal area impacted by this Project is considered unlikely to be utilized by salt marsh harvest mouse.

California Clapper Rail

The Project is near known suitable and occupied habitat of this species. There are five documented CNDDDB occurrences in marsh habitat within two miles of the Action Area (CNDDDB occurrence #34 from Arrowhead Marsh, #85 at the Martin Luther King Regional Shoreline, #33 in the marsh along south side of Alameda Island, #110 on the southeast shore of Alameda Island on San Leandro Bay, and #108 on the North side of Bay Farm Island along San Leandro Bay, Alameda) (CDFW 2022). Fan Marsh, directly south of the ROW from PM 17.44 to PM 18.02, contains abundant suitable habitat and harbors a known population of California clapper rails (Olofson Environmental, Inc. 2020). In 2019, 48 rail occurrences were recorded at Fan Marsh, resulting in a very highly dense population relative to marsh size of the species. In the 2021 survey report, 36 rail occurrences had been documented at Fan Marsh, with a density of 1.19 (rail per acre) (Olofson Environmental, Inc. 2021). The marsh is repeatedly known to be highly populated by the species.

The ruderal area impacted within the Project area is considered unlikely to be utilized by California clapper rail, but the adjacent marsh within the Action Area may be used by individuals during king tide events or as they move between suitable habitat patches and into upland refugia. Technical assistance with the Service on January 22, 2022, confirmed that California clapper rail should be considered to have high potential to occur within or near the Action Area.

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Effects of the Proposed Action

Effects of the action are all consequences to listed species or critical habitat that are caused by the proposed action, including the consequences of other activities that are caused by the proposed action. A consequence is caused by the proposed action if it would not occur but for the proposed action and it is reasonably certain to occur. Effects of the action may occur later in time and may include consequences occurring outside the immediate area involved in the action.

The Project has been designed to minimize the permanent and temporary impacts to listed species to the greatest extent possible while still installing the roadway improvements. Existing access roads will be used, and staging will be limited to ruderal vegetation, barren ground, and paved areas within the proposed construction area. All temporarily disturbed staging areas will be restored.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

Physical Project impacts are limited to 0.388 acre of urban landscaped and ruderal vegetative ground cover. Salt marsh harvest mouse are not expected to occur within this ruderal habitat during construction. Fencing and the presence of Service-Approved Biological Monitors will further minimize the likelihood mice will enter the construction areas.

Temporary effects to salt marsh harvest mice may occur through construction noise. Construction noise will affect 2.567 acres of coastal salt marsh within the Action Area between PM 17.44 to PM 18.02. It is expected that mice in this area are habituated to noise levels generated by vehicle traffic on SR 61, however, construction related noise will exceed the ambient noise level. This disturbance could potentially cause the species to move out of covered areas and expose themselves to predators. One benefit of the Project is the overall reduction in rolling traffic noise due to a smoother surface of SR 61. New pavement has shown to have an estimated -3 decibel (dB) reduction in traffic noise (Illingworth and Rodkin 2011) over the existing condition.

Vibration and soil movement resulting from construction activities should not have the potential to cause disturbance to salt marsh harvest mouse behavior. Studies have concluded that vibrational energy decreases fairly rapidly over distance from the source of disturbance (Attewell and Farmer 1973; Caltrans 2004). The road prism within the Project is likely compacted to at least 95 percent per industry standards and per Caltrans, will absorb construction related vibration, minimizing the potential for effects from vibration to mice adjacent to the Project in Fan Marsh.

Disturbance to females from March to November could result in consequences such as nest abandonment or failure of the current litter. Therefore, displaced salt marsh harvest mice will likely suffer from increased predation, competition, and potentially reduced reproductive success overall.

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The implementation of the *Conservation Measures* described in the *Description of the Proposed Action* section for the salt marsh harvest mouse will ensure the likelihood of harm, injury, and mortality resulting from the proposed actions remains low.

California Clapper Rail

The majority of Project impacts are limited to ruderal vegetative ground cover. California clapper rails are not expected to occur within the ruderal habitat, but are likely to occur within or near areas anticipated to be temporarily affected by noise and the presence of construction activities.

Temporary effects to California clapper rails would occur through noise and presence of construction activities adjacent to rail habitat at Fan Marsh (PM 17.44 to 18.02). Construction noise is estimated to exceed the ambient noise level of 60 dB in Fan Marsh at 800 feet from construction. It is estimated that all areas of Fan Marsh will receive temporary construction noise ranging from 85 dB to 61 dB. Elevated noise may result in rails flushing from cover and putting them at greater risk of predation. Noise may also have a masking effect that could hinder altering behavior and calls. Construction is estimated to take four months to complete between PM 17.44 to PM 18.02 on Doolittle Road. Even though construction will increase noise within the area, the Project will result in the overall reduction in rolling traffic noise due to a smoother surface of SR 61. New pavement has shown to have an estimated -3dB reduction in traffic noise over the existing condition (Illingworth and Rodkin 2011). Implementation of the *Conservation Measures*, including working outside of the breeding season, will minimize these adverse effects.

Cumulative Effects

Cumulative effects include the effects of future State, Tribal, local, or private actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the Action Area considered in this biological opinion. Future Federal actions that are unrelated to the proposed action are not considered in this section because they require separate consultation pursuant to section 7 of the Act. During this consultation, the Service did not identify any future non-Federal actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the Action Area of the proposed Project.

Conclusion

After reviewing the current *Status of Species* for the salt marsh harvest mouse and the California clapper rail, the *Environmental Baseline* for the Action Area, the *Effects of the Proposed Action*, and the *Cumulative Effects*, it is the Service's biological opinion that the State Route 61 Capital Preventative Maintenance Project, as proposed, is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the salt marsh harvest mouse or the California clapper rail. The Service reached this conclusion because the project-related effects to the species, when added to the *Environmental Baseline* and analyzed in consideration of all potential *Cumulative Effects*, will not rise to the level of reducing the likelihood of survival and recovery of these species based on the following: (1) no physical habitat loss is anticipated to result from the proposed Project, and (2) temporary noise effects from the proposed Project will not result in significant mortality or reduction in the population of salt marsh harvest mouse or California clapper rail in the area.

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INCIDENTAL TAKE STATEMENT

Section 9 of the Act and Federal regulation pursuant to section 4(d) of the Act prohibit the take of endangered and threatened species, respectively, without special exemption. Take is defined as to harass, harm, pursue, hunt, shoot, wound, kill, trap, capture or collect, or to attempt to engage in any such conduct. Harm in the definition of “take” in the Act means an act which actually kills or injures wildlife. Such [an] act may include significant habitat modification or degradation where it actually kills or injures wildlife by significantly impairing essential behavioral patterns, including breeding, feeding, or sheltering (50 CFR 17.3) Under the terms of section 7(b)(4) and section 7(o)(2), taking that is incidental to and not the purpose of the agency action is not considered to be prohibited taking under the Act provided that such taking is in compliance with the proposed protective measures and the terms and conditions of an incidental take statement and occurs as a result of the action as proposed.

The measures described below are non-discretionary, and must be undertaken by Caltrans so that they become binding conditions of any grant or permit issued to the applicant, as appropriate, for the exemption in section 7(o)(2) to apply. Caltrans has a continuing duty to regulate the activity covered by this incidental take statement. If Caltrans (1) fails to assume and implement the terms and conditions or (2) fails to require the applicant to adhere to the terms and conditions of the incidental take statement through enforceable terms that are added to the permit or grant document, the protective coverage of section 7(o)(2) may lapse. In order to monitor the impact of incidental take, Caltrans must report the progress of the action and its impact on these species to the Service as specified in the incidental take statement [50 CFR §402.14(i)(3)].

Amount or Extent of Take

The Service anticipates incidental take of salt marsh harvest mouse will be difficult to detect or quantify for the following reasons: the inherently elusive behavior, propensity to move rapidly through vegetation, and their cryptic occupancy of vegetation types resulting in low detectability. There is a risk of injury or mortality as a result of the proposed activities and subsequent temporary loss or degradation of suitable habitat from noise disturbance. Therefore, the Service anticipates take incidental to the proposed action in the form of harm from construction related noise which would impair essential behaviors like predator avoidance within 2.567 acres of suitable habitat.

The Service anticipates incidental take of California clapper rail will be difficult to detect or quantify for the following reasons: the inherently elusive behavior, propensity to move rapidly through vegetation, and their cryptic occupancy of vegetation types resulting in low detectability. There is a risk of injury or mortality as a result of the proposed activities and subsequent temporary loss or degradation of suitable habitat from noise disturbance. Therefore, the Service anticipates take incidental to the proposed action in the form of harm from construction related noise which would impair essential behaviors like predator avoidance within 2.567 acres of suitable habitat.

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Upon implementation of the following reasonable and prudent measures, incidental take of salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail associated with the project will become exempt from the prohibitions described in section 9 of the Act. No other forms of take are exempted under this opinion.

Effect of the Take

In the accompanying biological opinion, the Service determined that the level of anticipated take is not likely to jeopardize the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail.

Reasonable and Prudent Measure

All necessary and appropriate measures to avoid or minimize effects on the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail resulting from implementation of this project have been incorporated into the project's proposed *Conservation Measures*. Therefore, the Service believes the following reasonable and prudent measure is necessary and appropriate to minimize the incidental take of the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail:

- 1) All *Conservation Measures*, as described in the *Description of the Proposed Action* section of this biological opinion, shall be fully implemented and adhered to. Further, this reasonable and prudent measure shall be supplemented by the Term and Condition below.

Terms and Condition

In order to be exempt from the prohibitions of section 9 of the Act, Caltrans shall ensure compliance with the following term and condition, which implement the reasonable and prudent measure described above. This Term and Condition is non-discretionary.

- 1) Term and Condition 1 implements Reasonable and Prudent Measure 1:
 - A) Caltrans shall minimize the potential for harm, killing or other forms of take of the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail from project-related activities by implementation of the *Conservation Measures* proposed in the Description of the Proposed Action in this biological opinion.
 - B) Caltrans shall immediately notify the Service of any killed, injured, or entrapped salt marsh harvest mice or California clapper rails, within one (1) working day of the detection. Please contact Jana Affonso, Assistant Field Supervisor at: San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office, 650 Capitol Mall, Suite 8-300, Sacramento, California 95814 or by telephone at (916) 930-2664.
 - C) Caltrans shall educate and inform personnel involved in the project as to the *Conservation Measures* and Terms and Conditions in this biological opinion.
 - D) Caltrans shall comply with the reporting requirements of this biological opinion, including

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a post-construction report outlining how the *Conservation Measures* were implemented for this project.

- E) Caltrans shall ensure any personnel identified as biological monitors or biologists, who are responsible for ensuring compliance with the *Conservation Measures* or other parts of the project which may affect federally-listed species, be Service-approved prior to implementing those activities.

Reporting Requirements

In order to monitor whether the amount or extent of incidental take anticipated from implementation of the project is approached or exceeded, Caltrans shall adhere to the following reporting requirements. Should this anticipated amount or extent of incidental take be exceeded, Caltrans must reinitiate formal consultation as per 50 CFR § 402.16.

- 1) The Service must be notified within 24 hours of the finding of any injured or dead listed species or any unanticipated damage to its habitat associated with the proposed project. Injured listed species shall be cared by a licensed veterinarian or other qualified person, such as the Service-approved biologist for the proposed project. Notification will be made to the contact above in Term and Condition 1B, and must include the date, time, and precise location of the individual/incident clearly indicated on a USGS 7.5 minute quadrangle or other maps at a finer scale, as requested by the Service, and any other pertinent information. When an injured or dead individual of the listed species is found, Caltrans shall follow the steps outlined in the Salvage and Disposition of Individuals Taken section below.
- 2) Sightings of any listed or sensitive animal species shall be reported to the Service and the CNDDDB (<https://www.wildlife.ca.gov/Data/CNDDDB/Submitting-Data>).

Salvage and Disposition of Individuals

Injured listed species must be cared for by a licensed veterinarian or other qualified person(s), such as the Service-approved biologist. Dead individuals must be sealed in a resealable plastic bag containing a paper with the date and time when the animal was found, the location where it was found, and the name of the person who found it, and the bag containing the specimen frozen in a freezer located in a secure site, until instructions are received from the Service regarding the disposition of the dead specimen. The Service contact person is Jana Affonso, Assistant Field Supervisor at: San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office, 650 Capitol Mall, Suite 8-300, Sacramento, California 95814 or by telephone at (916) 930-2664.

CONSERVATION RECOMMENDATIONS

Section 7(a)(1) of the Act directs Federal agencies to utilize their authorities to further the purposes of the Act by carrying out conservation programs for the benefit of endangered and threatened species. Conservation recommendations are discretionary agency activities to minimize or avoid adverse effects of a proposed action on listed species or critical habitat, to help implement recovery plans, or to develop information. The Service recommends the

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following actions:

- 1) Encourage or require the use of appropriate California native species in restoration efforts.
- 2) Facilitate additional educational programs geared toward the importance and conservation of tidal marsh and seasonal wetlands.
- 3) Assist the Service with implementing other recovery actions identified within the most current recovery plans for salt marsh harvest mouse.
- 4) Participate in programs being developed by the Federal and State resource agencies to limit and reverse the spread of non-native species, such as *Phragmites*, *Lepidium*, clams, and other invasive species.

In order for the Service to be kept informed of actions minimizing or avoiding adverse effects or benefiting listed species or their habitats, the Service requests notification of the implementation of any conservation recommendations.

REINITIATION – CLOSING STATEMENT

This concludes formal consultation on the State Route 61 Capital Preventative Maintenance Project. As provided in 50 CFR § 402.16,

(a) Reinitiation of consultation is required and shall be requested by the Federal agency or by the Service, where discretionary Federal involvement or control over the action has been retained or is authorized by law and:

- (1) If the amount or extent of taking specified in the incidental take statement is exceeded;
- (2) If new information reveals effects of the action that may affect listed species or critical habitat in a manner or to an extent not previously considered;
- (3) If the identified action is subsequently modified in a manner that causes an effect to the listed species or critical habitat that was not considered in the biological opinion or written concurrence; or
- (4) If a new species is listed or critical habitat designated that may be affected by the identified action.

(b) An agency shall not be required to reinitiate consultation after the approval of a land management plan prepared pursuant to 43 U.S.C. 1712 or 16 U.S.C. 1604 upon listing of a new species or designation of new critical habitat if the land management plan has been adopted by the agency as of the date of listing or designation, provided that any authorized actions that may affect the newly listed species or designated critical habitat will be addressed through a separate action-specific consultation. This exception to reinitiation of consultation shall not apply to those

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land management plans prepared pursuant to 16 U.S.C. 1604 if:

(1) Fifteen years have passed since the date the agency adopted the land management plan prepared pursuant to 16 U.S.C. 1604; and

(2) Five years have passed since the enactment of Public Law 115-141 [March 23, 2018] or the date of the listing of a species or the designation of critical habitat, whichever is later.

If you have any questions regarding this biological opinion, please contact Andrew Raabe, Fish and Wildlife Biologist (Andrew_Raabe@fws.gov) or Kim Squires, Section 7 Division Manager (Kim_Squires@fws.gov) at the letterhead address or at or at 916-930-5603. Please reference the Service File Number 2022-0035037 in any correspondence regarding this project.

Sincerely,

Donald Ratcliff
Field Supervisor

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